

DMP for Use case 7 - Fire Hazard

Version : 2 – 2025/04/28

This Data Management Plan aims to provide a brief description of the model and datasets associated with use case 7 - Fire Hazard.

DMP Authors/Contacts

GEO.INFORMED partner: INBO

Main stakeholder: ANB

DMP Language

English

1 Brief description of the use case

The Agency Nature and Forest (ANB) is responsible for wildfire prevention in nature and forest areas. Wildfire behavior depends strongly on the **fuel load** that is available. Although fuel load is the variable that can most easily be managed to reduce fire propagation, it is often overlooked or greatly simplified in operational wildfire assessment systems. It would however be of great value to spatially describe this key factor that fire managers can control. In Flanders, heathland ecosystems are particularly vulnerable to wildfires. ***Molinia caerulea*** (purple moor grass) is a grass species that can become invasive in (dry) heathlands as a response to eutrophication, especially by nitrogen.

In this use case, we aim to map the extent and the biomass of *Molinia caerulea*, an invasive grass species, in (dry) heathlands in the Campine region of Flanders.

1.1 What needs to be monitored?

The coverage and/or the volume of *Molinia caerulea*

1.2 Where should it be monitored?

In heathland areas in Flanders (mainly found in the Campine region)

1.3 How often should it be monitored?

Every 1-5 years

2 Modeling approach

2.1 What type of deep learning problem?

Classification: Label each pixel based on the time series of Sentinel-2 vegetation indices (NDVI & NDMI)

2.2 Which model type(s) were used?

Random Forest

3 Data

3.1 Which input data were used?

Sentinel-2 time series of vegetation indices and/or 10m + 20m bands.

Centered around the month of the field campaign (August 2022), starting 15 months before (May 2021) and ending 14 months after (October 2023) this central month. For the MNAE dataset (see section 3.2), the central month is also August, and the time series also starts in May the year before and runs until October the year after.

Preprocessing was done in OpenEO:

- kernel-based cloud masking
- vegetation index calculation
- temporal compositing (monthly/dekadal)
- linear interpolation

Afterwards, a Savitzky-Golay smoothing was performed in Python.

3.2 Which reference data were used?

General description:

The study site for this use case is the Campine region

The reference data consist of field plots from two main sources:

- Field campaign 2022 in four Natura-2000 Special Conservation Zones within the Campine region of Flanders (FC-2022)
- Measurement Network Abiotic Environment (MNAE) obtained from the Research Institute Nature and Forest (INBO), spread across all (known) heathland areas in Flanders

In the figure below, you can see the location of the study area (Campine region) in Flanders, as well as the location of the field plots from the FC-2022 and the MNAE dataset.

3.2.1 Dataset 1

Dataset name or title: Molinia Heathlands: Field campaign 2022 (FC-2022.geojson)

Dataset abstract:

An extensive field campaign was conducted in August of 2022, when ground reference data were collected in four heathland areas across the Campine region (De Teut, Terhaagdoornheide, Averbode and De Maten). During this field campaign, per heathland area 40 plots were selected across the total range of Molinia coverage (%) present in the respective area. We made sure that each reference plot was located in relatively homogenous vegetation patch. The reference plots were circular with a radius of 5 meter. Within each plot, the coverage of *M. caerulea* was visually estimated in 10% bins. We will refer to this dataset as the FC-2022 dataset, containing 160 plots.

Dataset locator: [10.5281/zenodo.15297227](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15297227)

Resource language: English

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

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Data format: geojson

Geometry: points

The attributes refer to a plot with radius of 5 meters around these points.

Coordinate reference system (CRS): WGS84

Geographic bounding box:

westBoundLongitude: 4.990389

eastBoundLongitude: 5.623371

southBoundLatitude: 50.942647

northBoundLatitude: 51.071480

Temporal extent: 2022-08-01 until 2022-08-16

Date of last revision: 2024-04-19

Lineage: The data were collected in the summer of 2022 by thesis student Victor Wepener, using the ESRI Collector app. Photos of the plots were also added, these were saved separately, in a folder system where the name of the subfolder equals the OBJECTID.

Attributes:

In the table below, all attributes are listed. The type 'categories' has the following classes:

- < 5%
- 5-14%
- 15-24%
- 25-34%
- 35-44%
- 45-54%
- 55-64%
- 65-74%
- 75-84%
- 85-94%
- >= 95%

The column 'Edited' (boolean) indicates whether this attribute was entered into the database while on the field. Attributes with N are automatically created by the system.

Name in geojson	Full name	Description	Type	Edited
Date	Date	date of field visit	date	Y
Perc_Molin	% Molinia	coverage of only the Molinia grass	categories	Y
Perc_all_g	% all grasses	coverage of all grasses (not other herbs)	categories	Y
Perc_trees	% trees	coverage of trees > 6m high	categories	Y
Perc_mosse	% mosses	coverage of mosses that are not covered by other vegetation	categories	Y
Perc_dwarf	% dwarf shrubs	coverage of the specific dry and wet heath shrubs	categories	Y
Perc_bare	% bare soil	coverage of soil that is not covered by vegetation	categories	Y
Remarks	remarks	open text field	text	Y
GlobalID	global ID	automatic ID	integer	N
created_us	user created	name of the user that created this sample	text	N
created_da	date created	date when this sample was created	date	N
last_edite	user last edit	name of the user that last edited this sample	text	N

last_edi_1	date last edit	date when this sample was last edited	date	N
OBJECTID	ID of the plot	unique identifier code given to each plot	integer	Y
Perc_herb	% herb layer	coverage of all vegetation < 0.5m (except mosses) that is not covered by other vegetation	categories	Y
Perc_shrub	% shrub layer	coverage of all vegetation > 0.5m and < 6m that is not covered by other vegetation	categories	Y
Perc_dead	% dead biomass	percentage of all biomass in the plot that is dead (only if whole plant is dead)	categories	Y
height_her	Height herb layer	average height of the herb layer in cm	integer	Y
height_shr	Height shrub layer	average height of the shrub layer in cm	integer	Y

Quality flags: not available

Number of samples in the dataset: 160

Size of the dataset: 94 KB

Screenshot of attribute table: Only a subset of the attributes and plots are visible in this screenshot.

	Date	Perc_Molin	Perc_all_g	Perc_trees	Perc_mosse	Perc_dwarf	Perc_bare_	Remarks	GlobalID	created_us	created_da	last_edite
1	1/08/2022	15-24%	< 5%	0%	5-14%	35-44%	< 5%	NULL	{A4CCD861-EC...	victor.wepener	1/08/2022	victor.wepener
2	1/08/2022	< 5%	5-14%	0%	< 5%	75-84%	< 5%	NULL	{5D841783-AE1...	victor.wepener	1/08/2022	victor.wepener
3	1/08/2022	35-44%	< 5%	0%	< 5%	25-34%	15-24%	NULL	{3782AAC7-3E...	victor.wepener	1/08/2022	victor.wepener
4	1/08/2022	25-34%	< 5%	0%	< 5%	35-44%	15-24%	NULL	{64FBF2F1-213...	victor.wepener	1/08/2022	victor.wepener
5	1/08/2022	< 5%	15-24%	0%	15-24%	5-14%	85-94%	NULL	{EAEDCF4E-F23...	victor.wepener	1/08/2022	victor.wepener
6	1/08/2022	15-24%	5-14%	0%	< 5%	35-44%	5-14%	NULL	{CABE215B-E47...	victor.wepener	1/08/2022	victor.wepener
7	1/08/2022	25-34%	35-44%	0%	< 5%	25-34%	< 5%	NULL	{34787C86-E22...	victor.wepener	1/08/2022	victor.wepener
8	1/08/2022	15-24%	5-14%	< 5%	< 5%	55-64%	< 5%	NULL	{3E535AC2-EFC...	victor.wepener	1/08/2022	victor.wepener
9	1/08/2022	< 5%	< 5%	0%	35-44%	55-64%	< 5%	NULL	{4E3E73F1-B96...	victor.wepener	1/08/2022	victor.wepener

Accessibility: Publicly available online

License (if applicable): CC0

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up. They are also available on Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.15297227](https://zenodo.org/record/10.5281/zenodo.15297227)

Are there any accompanying files? Yes, photos of the plots. They are saved in a folder system where the subfolder names equal the OBJECTID. Note that photos are available only for a subset of the plots visited. The folder structure and a small preview of the photos are given below. These photos are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

📁 ID 402 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3214 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3621 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4418 ✓ 👤
📁 ID 403 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3215 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3622 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4419 ✓ 👤
📁 ID 404 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3216 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3623 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4420 ✓ 👤
📁 ID 405 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3217 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3624 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4421 ✓ 👤
📁 ID 406 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3218 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3625 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4422 ✓ 👤
📁 ID 407 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3219 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4014 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4423 ✓ 👤
📁 ID 408 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3220 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4015 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4424 ✓ 👤
📁 ID 409 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3221 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4016 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4425 ✓ 👤
📁 ID 410 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3222 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4017 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4426 ✓ 👤
📁 ID 411 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 3223 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4018 ✓ 👤	📁 ID 4427 ✓ 👤

3.2.2 Dataset 2

Dataset name or title: Measurement Network Abiotic Environment (MNAE.geojson)

Dataset abstract: This measurement network is set up by the Flemish Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO) and operational since 2014. The plots in this network were selected through a spatially balanced sampling design over all known heathland habitats in Flanders, and consists of square plots of 3 by 3 meters. The Molinia coverage within these plots is estimated using the Londo decimal scale for relevés of permanent quadrats. From this network, only the plots measured from 2017 to 2023 were used. We will refer to this dataset as the MNAE dataset, containing 401 plots. The exact number of plots for each measurement year can be found in the table below.

Year	Name of file	Nr. of plots
2017		92
2018		108
2019		86
2020		-
2021		-
2022		69
2023		46
TOTAL		401

Dataset locator: [10.5281/zenodo.15297427](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15297427)

Resource language: English

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

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Data format: geojson

Geometry: points

The attributes refer to a plot of 3x3 meter of which the point location is the southeastern corner.

Coordinate reference system (CRS): WGS84

Geographic bounding box:*westBoundLongitude:* 4.990389*eastBoundLongitude:* 5.623371*southBoundLatitude:* 50.942647*northBoundLatitude:* 51.071480**Temporal extent:** 2017-04-27 until 2023-09-20**Date of last revision:** 2024-04-19**Lineage:** The data were collected in the frame of the measurement network LSVI. More details about this measurement network can be found in Westra et al. 2019 ¹.

The **plot locations**, only for those plots located in heathland, were provided as csv files by Toon Westra (INBO). that were converted into geojson format. These files contain the `plot_id`, the heathland type `'type_observed'` (= Natura2000 habitat code), the date of the field assessment `'date_assessment'` and the x,y coordinates in Lambert 72.

The **measured attributes** were delivered as separate csv files. They contain a complete vegetation survey in Londo scale. Per line, there is the `plot_id`, the name of the plant, both Dutch and scientific, and a **'cover_mean'** which is the center of the recorded Londo interval. Based on the `plot_id`, the `cover_mean` of *Molinia caerulea* was linked to the plot locations of the same year.

Attributes: The attributes of the final dataset are listed in the table below.

Name in geojson	Full name	Description	Type
<code>plot_id</code>	ID of the plot	unique identifier code given to each plot	integer
<code>Date</code>	Date	date of field visit	date
<code>type</code>	Habitat type	recorded habitat type of the plot	integer
<code>x</code>	X coordinate	X coordinate in Lambert 72	float
<code>y</code>	Y coordinate	Y coordinate in Lambert 72	float

¹ Westra, Toon, An Leyssen, Patrik Oosterlynck, Els Lommelen, Jeroen Vanden Borre, Steven De Saeger, Bart Vandevoorde, Arno Thomaes, Sam Provoost, and Desiré Paelinckx. 2019. "Analyse van de gegevens van het meetnet habitatkwaliteit ten behoeve van de rapportage voor de Habitatrictlijn (periode 2013-2018)." <https://doi.org/10.21436/inbor.16581110>.

cover_mean	% cover mean	mean coverage of Molinia, based on the recorded Londo interval, in percentage	integer
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Quality flags: not available

Number of samples in the dataset: 401

Size of the dataset: 99 KB

Screenshot of attribute table: Only a subset of the attributes and plots are visible in this screenshot.

	plot_id	type	x	y	cover_mean	Date
1	95218	4030	237053.51	183726.12	0	4/27/2017
2	551218	2310	225181.58	182286.15	2	6/28/2017
3	1272114	2330_dw	225373.58	182542.22	1	6/29/2017
4	1501490	2330_bu	225917.66	182830.17	40	6/29/2017
5	1599794	4010	225245.54	182414.1	40	6/29/2017
6	158002	2310	225661.55	182094.11	1	6/30/2017
7	47666	4030	227453.55	184942.06	0	6/30/2017

Accessibility: Publically available online

License (if applicable): CC0

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up. They are also available on Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.15297427](https://zenodo.org/record/10.5281/zenodo.15297427)

Are there any accompanying files? No